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Jean Monnet Module

International Business: Strategies for Integrated Europe

With the support of the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

COURSE SYLLABUS

COURSE INFORMATION

Module	Erasmus Module in International Business
Title	International Business – European Dimension
Structure	24 teaching hours

PROFESSOR INFORMATION

Professor	Oksana Galak, PhD
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COURSE PREREQUISITES

Course is read at the advanced level for the master's students. Students are supposed to have a prior knowledge of main concepts related to the strategic activities of organizations operating at the domestic level. Building upon this knowledge, this course applies the relevant concepts in the context of EU business practices.

COURSE DESCRIPTION

The goal of this course is to familiarize students with a broad range of theoretical and practical perspectives on the environment, strategies, and organization of the European businesses.

The course is offered within the Jean Monnet Programme with the support of the European Commission.

Jean Monnet was one of the founding fathers of the European Union and a strong proponent of European integration. This program has a long history and has recently celebrated 30 years of successful funding for the projects all over the world.¹

Building upon the core courses in the International Business curriculum, the goal of this elective course is to deepen the students' understanding of the role of environment in organizational decision-making with specific application to the case of EU. EU-wide institutional initiatives create and constantly alter the "rules of the game" for the European businesses. Thus, the main question of the course is "What were / are / will be the benefits and challenges of the European integration for BUSINESS?"

Throughout the course the students are expected to develop theory-based skills in evaluating the opportunities and threats in the complex multicultural environments of international firms, in analysing the resources of firms, and in bringing up the solutions in the form of the international competitive strategies. All these aspects of firms functioning are going to be presented and discussed in their connection to the field of EU Business and Economic Studies.

The core feature of this course is a strong focus on the link between theoretical concepts learnt during the lectures and their practical applications in the real-world environments by real firms. To highlight this link, the theoretical concepts are being consistently explained using the multiple examples of the EU companies currently operating in the global environment.

Even more importantly, during the course the students are supposed to work in small groups on the business cases illustrating the challenges and opportunities related to the specifics of the EU environment, governance structures of the EU firms, their internationalization strategies, and innovation trends. Working through the histories of internationally well-known EU companies, analysing the reasons for

¹ <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/opportunities/opportunities-for-organisations/jean-monnet-actions>
https://europa.eu/european-union/sites/europa.eu/files/eu_pioneers_jean_monnet_en.pdf
https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/history/eu-pioneers_en#jean_monnet

their failures and successes, students can use their knowledge to test the applicability of theoretical concepts and come with viable and scientifically based solutions for the future.

The course is delivered primarily through lectures and discussions of the specific sub-topics as well as the preparation and presentations of business cases. Each student is strongly encouraged to participate in the class discussions. Additional questions for in-class debates are provided in the Academic calendar below.

Classroom participation, both during lectures and seminars, is an important part of evaluation. A suggestion to read the assigned material from the reference books and articles, and to express opinions, comments, and insights relative to the discussion topic is to be made.

MAIN TEXTBOOKS AND MATERIALS

Required Readings:

JOHNSON, D., & TURNER, C. (2016). European business. London: Routledge.

CLARKE, T., & CHANLAT, J. F. (2009). European Corporate Governance: readings and perspectives. London: Routledge.

MANDL, I., & PATRINI, V. (2018). European born globals: job creation in young international businesses. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.

PENG, M. W. (2014). Global strategic management. Third edition, International edition. South-Western Cengage Learning.

SOMERS, F. (2019) European Business Environment. Taylor & Francis.

SOMERS, F., DAVIS-OST, K., FRENCKEN, J. and HEUTEN, E. (2019). European Competition. Taylor & Francis.

SUDER, G., & LINDEQUE, J. (2018). Doing Business in Europe. Third Edition. SAGE

Additional Readings:

CAVUSGIL, S. T., KNIGHT, G., & RIESENBERGER, J. R. (2014). International business: The new realities. Harlow, Pearson Education Limited.

DAFT, R. L. (2016). Organization theory & design. Boston, MA Cengage Learning

Other Materials: Other class materials such as lecture slides and handouts are to be made available before the actual start of the classes / particluar sessions.

ACADEMIC CALENDAR

Lecture 1	3 TH
Topic	General Introduction of the Course Major Theoretical Approaches
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 1. A Portrait of Europe
In Peng (2014)	Chapter 1: Strategy Around the Globe
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of Industrial Forces in Strategic Decisions of the Firms • Building VRIO Resources • European Institutions through the lens of Neo-Institutional View
Advanced In-Class Debate	Integrated Model of IO, RBV and IV
Lecture 2	4 TH
Topic	Past and Present of European Integration
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 3. The Evolution of European Integration
In Suder and Lindeque (2018)	Chapter 2. Landmarks of European Integration: How History and Politics Shape the Business Environment
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What Is Economic Integration? • Single European Market / Single Currency • EU Enlargement
Advanced In-Class Debates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Common Agricultural Policy: history and current state - UK and the EU: from rebates to Brexit and beyond
Lecture 3	3 TH
Topic	Internationalization Strategies of the EU Firms
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 15. Europe in A Global Context
In Suder and Lindeque (2018)	Chapter 5. The Europeanisation of Business Environment

Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case of Airbus – A successful example of the Effects of European Integration
Advanced In-Class Debate	European Champions: A Model for the Future?
Lecture 4	4 TH
Topic	Competition policy in the EU
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 6. European competition policy: The guardian of integrated markets
In Somers et al. (2019)	Chapter 1. Competition and Competition Policy Chapter 2. Dominance and Market Power
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • History and Developments in the Competition Policy • Extraterritorial Reach & Private Enforcement
Advanced In-Class Debate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Fight Against Cartels - Examples of the Recent Cases of Anticompetitive Behaviour and Counteractions of the Commission
Lecture 5	2 TH
Topic	Industrial Policy in the EU
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 7. Promoting Structural Change: EU Industrial and Enterprise Policy Chapter 12. EU Environment Policy: A Green Light for Competitiveness?
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial Policy in the Last Decades • Recent Developments in the Industrial Policy
Advanced In-Class Debate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dependencies And Ways of Handling Them - Industrial Alliances
Lecture 6	2 TH
Topic	Digitalization as EU Priority
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	

	Chapter 13. A Digital Agenda for Europe: Creating the Inclusive Information Economy
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in the Creation of the European Information Society
Advanced In-Class Debate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Compass and the challenges of implementation DECI and inter-country comparisons
Lecture 7	2 TH
Topic	Managing People in Europe
Reference Chapters: In Johnson and Turner (2016)	Chapter 14. European labour markets and the search for flexibility
In Somers (2013)	Chapter 8. The free movement of people and international business strategy
Topic Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Work Directive Rights of the workers
Advanced In-Class Debate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posted workers. Individual Learning accounts
Lecture 8	4 TH
Topic	Presentations of the Case Projects. Course Feedback.

GRADING POLICIES

Grading Formula

- Team-based Business Case Project
 - 35% - Case Text
 - 15% - Presentation
- 15% - Participation and feedback
- 35% - Take-home essay

Grading Scheme	
89 – 100	1
76 – 88	2
63 – 75	3
51 – 62	4
0 – 50	5

Minimum attendance requirement - 75% of classes.

Lecture Slides, relevant readings, and supplementary materials are to be provided on Moodle before each lecture.

For some sessions, students may be asked to read the selected case studies/policy documents prior to the class. The materials will be provided for reading in advance.

CASE STUDY WRITING

Companies' strategies are influenced by the environments they operate in. Europe has grown from customs union to economic and monetary union. European businesses enjoy the “four freedoms”, but also face the impact of the EU-wide industrial, competition, innovation, environmental and other policies. Thus, it is undisputable, that the integration processes within the EU have been influencing the strategies of the companies. The questions raised in this course is how this has been happening and what it means and will mean for the European business in the future.

In this Project the students are expected to answer these questions by writing a Case Study about one industry or one company operating in Europe.

The expected length of the Case Study text is 15-20 pages. The grading of the text is done by the lecturer. The results are presented to the class. The presentation should last between 20-30 minutes. The grading of the presentation is done by averaging the anonymous evaluations provided by the peers - max 15 points. Grading of the colleagues' presentations earns the students points for each evaluation.

The grading of the Business Cases is based on the following criteria:

- Clarity and structure of the presentation of the general context and main question of the case study.
- Clarity of the link between practical problem set in the case and theoretical concept used for finding the solution.

- Use of proper sourcing in the argumentation (both the case text itself and additional resources if necessary)
- Creativity in presenting the discussion.

The students are also provided with the Case Writing Guidelines with more detailed information.

Students decide themselves on the workload distribution within their Teams, but they must make sure that:

- There is one contact person responsible for communication with the lecturer, uploading info on Moodle, and other administrative issues.
- Every group member participates in preparation of the assignments and can (but not obliged to) present the case.

At least one consultation meeting of the Team with the lecturer is expected. For that the students are expected to propose a few options for date/time when at least 2/3 of the team members are available. Students are encouraged to invite the representatives of the focus company for a guest lecture (and as a witness to their presentation).

COURSE POLICIES

- Students are required to arrive in class in time.
- If students must leave class earlier, they should let the lecturer know beforehand.
- The assignments should be submitted in due time: late submissions are not going to be accepted.
- Students are continuously informed and updated via the Announcements tool on Moodle. They are expected to check Moodle and their emails regularly.
- Students are recommended not to use phones during the sessions (also for texting).
- Participation is strongly encouraged and rewarded.
- The critique, feedback and suggestions should be constructive and the communication respectful towards each other.
- To ensure the timely and fair access to the information for all team members, the students are expected to only use the Team Forums for all Team-related correspondence with the lecturer (not email).
- If there are questions, problems, concerns, students are welcome to discuss them with the lecturer either personally or via email.

Methodological Guidelines and Recommendations

GENERAL COURSE FORUM

Already in the beginning of the course, the students are provided with various tool allowing them to communicate both among themselves and with the lecturer. First of all, they are offered a communication tool in form of Forum (on the learning platform Moodle). This tool allows them to post questions which will be immediately visible to all participants of the course. Those are encouraged to answer the questions of colleagues. If this is not possible the lecturer responds to the question.

This tool is available throughout the whole semester.

PARTICIPATION

The students are informed that the participation is evaluated:

- by the lecturer based on frequency and quality of students' contributions, and
- via a self-evaluation tool on Moodle

The latter allows the students to provide the self-evaluations of their participation in each session. The students can access the tool and save the intermediate evaluations as often as they wish. However, they are recommended to do it right after each session, when they still remember how active they were in the class.

In the suggested form (see below), the students are asked to select the statement which is in their opinion the best description of the situation.

Which statement is true for the session on 8.03.2022?

- I attended, but didn't participate.
- I participated.
- I participated actively.
- I missed the session.

For the regular lectures only, the participation is graded. Still, even if the students didn't participate, they need to indicate, whether they attended the classes (to crosscheck the information accumulated via the attendance lists signed during the class).

GET-TO-KNOW SURVEY

In the beginning of the course the students can be asked to fill in the Get-to-Know survey. Such Survey might be designed using the tools offered by the learning platform Moodle or alternatively based on such platforms as Mentimeter, Slido, etc.

Get-to-Know Survey

Seite 1

1 Which statement best describes your status at the UniWien?
Auswählen ...

2 Which country do you come from?
Bearbeiten Ansicht Einfügen Format Werkzeuge Tabelle Hilfe
p

3 Which semester of your studies are you in?
Kein Tausendertrennzeichen verwenden.

4 What is your "major" (main direction of studies)?

5 What is your "minor" (complementary direction of studies)?

6 Have you already taken / are you taking now the course KU "Principles of International Business" (MA)?
 Ja Nein Keine Antwort

Seite 2

7 Have you heard about this course from your peers?
 Ja Nein Keine Antwort

8 What is your motivation to join this course?
Bearbeiten Ansicht Einfügen Format Werkzeuge Tabelle Hilfe
p

Seite 3

9 Please state how much you agree with the following statement:
"I have read and analysed many Business Case Studies in other courses"
 Agree Partly agree Disagree Keine Antwort

10 Please state how much you agree with the following statement:
"I have experience of *writing* a Business Case Study"
 Agree Partly agree Disagree Keine Antwort

Seite 4

11 If you have any preference regarding the colleagues you want to work with, please list their names below. If you don't have any preferences, just leave this questions open.

Seite 5

12 Which grade do you strive to get on this course?
 1
 2
 3
 4
 Keine Antwort

13 Do you have any questions you would like to ask me at this point? Then just type them in the space provided below.
Bearbeiten Ansicht Einfügen Format Werkzeuge Tabelle Hilfe
p

The purpose of this short survey is three-fold:

- to provide the lecturer with the relevant information for the organization of the course (e.g., how much knowledge of IB-related concepts the students have or how much experience they have with the case studies)
- to let students get to know each other, and
- to let the lecturer know about students' preferences regarding the composition of the course project teams.

After the submission of the individual answers, the students can see the answers of their colleagues.

Students are made aware of the fact that they can skip any question they wish, but the more questions are answered – the better.

TEAMWORK

The course has a strong focus on the teamwork and the main assignment of the course is also team based. Each Team consists of 4-5 people (depending on the overall size of the class). If the students have certain preferences regarding the colleagues they want to work with, those can be taken account of (the students inform the lecture via the Get-to-Know Survey – see above). The lecturer builds the teams using random allocation (if the students do not have any preferences) and informs the students about the team composition.

Each Team is provided with the access to the Team FORUM. This is a communication and collaboration tool, which can be accessed only by the members of the Team and the lecturer. The students are requested to conduct all correspondence related to their project via Team FORUM (and not via the email). This ensures the fair access to the information for all Team members.

Each Team after internal consultations is expected to fill in the Survey regarding their Team project (see below the example of the Company Selection Tool). Before that the students should be informed about the following points:

- To write the Case Study, you need to have access to the information about the company. While the relevant data can be often found online (in annual reports, on corporate websites, in the articles published in the press, etc.), combining it with the information gathered through the personal communication with representatives of the company offers a better insight.
- If the interviews are planned, the potential interview partners should be ideally in the managerial positions, as the questions you are going to ask will require strategic insights. If you don't have any contacts, keep in mind that there are many excellent Case Studies based exclusively on the publicly available sources. Just ensure that you have access to the relevant data.
- The choice of the company shouldn't necessarily be limited to only one location. Any European company, or even a non-European one (but having EU presence) can become a focus of the analysis. Even if you are planning to conduct the interviews with the company representatives, online ways of communication allow us to reach the people in different parts of the world easier.
- Note that analysing some industries might represent additional challenges due to the nature of their business. For example, banking and insurance companies represent very interesting cases, as they are strongly influenced by the EU institutional framework and need to adjust their strategies accordingly. However, the nature of these frameworks is very specific and might requires some knowledge of finance and banking.
- It will be your decision as a team whether you focus on only one company or choose to have a broader coverage focusing on several companies. The latter approach might be beneficial especially in case if you are not able to contact the companies directly. Then each company's "story" may be shorter, illustrating one-two aspects of its strategy. The stronger focus in this case may be put on the industry as a whole. Industry-level data and regulations are usually easier to find.

Example of a Company Selection Tool.

CHOICE OF COMPANIES

1* Please write here the name of the most preferred company you would like to focus on in your TEAM CASE PROJECT.

2* Do you have personal access to the first-hand data about your preferred company?
 Ja Nein

3 If you answered yet to the previous question, please elaborate briefly. Do you work for the company? What kind of contact (with whom) would you be able to establish?

Bearbeiten Ansicht Einfügen Format Werkzeuge Tabelle Hilfe

4* In which country is the company (company's HQ) located?

5* Please briefly describe the company in terms of size, international scope and potential interest for the course. Providing the company website might be very useful at this stage.

Bearbeiten Ansicht Einfügen Format Werkzeuge Tabelle Hilfe

6* Please write here the name of the alternative company (second best option) you might focus on in your TEAM CASE PROJECT.

At the same time, the lecturer shares with the students the Case Writing Guidelines (provided in the set of Teaching support materials)

Also, some examples of the case studies (see the set of case studies) can be made available on Moodle. The students are encouraged to look through the texts to get an understanding of what a Case Study might look like, but they are urged to consider those only as suggestions and not as prescriptions for their own research.

CASE STUDY GRADING

The work on the Case Study assignments includes two types of output:

- The presentation delivered in class.
- The final text submitted via Moodle (uploaded into the designated folder)

The performance of the Teams on the presentations is evaluate by their colleagues.

There are two parts of the evaluation. In the first - mandatory - part of the evaluation the students are expected to assign points for the quality of the content & structure and for the quality of the presentation delivery. For the example of the interface, please see on the right:

In the second - optional - part of the evaluation the students can provide comments on their grading and earn points towards their grade.

The evaluations are anonymous, i.e., the individual numerical evaluations are not made visible to the colleagues. As soon as the last presentation is evaluated, the lecturer posts the average scores for each Team on Moodle and shares the most constructive feedback and comments (keeping the anonymity of the reviewer).

The evaluation tool can be accessed throughout the whole presentation period and the students can change their evaluations as often as they wish before the deadline set by the lecturer.

How do you evaluate the **quality of the content**? Was the main focus of the case well communicated? Do you feel that the case presentation gave you some good insights into the topic? Have you learned anything relevant for this course and for you personally?

Please evaluate

from **1 (point)** - very low quality (the focus is not well-communicated / no relevant insights)

to **10 (points)** - very high quality (clear focus / useful insights)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

How would you evaluate **the presentation structure and delivery**? Was the material presented in a comprehensive and engaging manner? Were the slides well-organised?

Please rate

from **1 (point)** - low quality (difficult to follow / not engaging / overloaded slides)

to **5 (points)** - high quality (highly engaging / well-communicated / attractive slides)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

TAKE-HOME ESSAY

- The short essay on one of the topics related to the European integration with focus on Sustainability and Digitalization
- The topics are to be assigned in the last part of the course. Students have 10 days to write and submit the Essay.
- The overall length of the text should be about 4-5 pages (12 point Times New Roman font, single spaced page).
- Deadline for submission - upload into the designated folder on Moodle – by _____.

No.	TOPIC	COMMENTS
1	Theoretical background of integration: definitions, forms, stages	This topic has a general focus and does not require an extensive discussion of the EU. It should be based on the general literature about the different forms of integration, from economic to political, and different stages through which countries and regions proceed in the integration process. Examples of integration (country blocks) are expected, but should be kept relatively short, with references to the sources for further information.
2	History of integration in the EU	Progression of integration in the EU, main Treaties, and their role for business. From Treaty of Paris to the Single European Act (1952-1987) and further from Treaty on European Union till today (1993-2023).
3	Different types of Market Groups within the EU	Discussion of historical development and current state of such groupings as EFTA, CEFTA, VISEGRAD, SHENGEN, etc.
4	Single European Market (SEM): from early days to current challenges and achievements	Discussion of the concept of SEM, challenges of the SEM as outlined in the Delors' paper, the recent analysis and the actions directed at improving SEM.
5	Common Agricultural Policy	History of action, pros and cons, controversies, and success. The latest developments in CAP, e.g., support of sustainable farming, Farm-to-Fork strategy, etc.

No.	TOPIC	COMMENTS
6	Competition Policy and how it influences business	This topic has a general focus and does not require an extensive discussion of the EU. It should be based on the general literature about the different forms, content, and structure of competition policies. Examples from different countries outside of the EU are welcome, but should be kept relatively short, with references to the sources for further information.
7	Competition Policy in the EU: focus on "anticompetitive behaviour"	Focus on such issues as the abuse of dominant position and cartels. Actions prohibited and allowed. Please discuss at least three examples.
8	Competition Policy in the EU: focus on "state aid"	Focus on such issue as the state aid and actions prohibited and allowed according to the EU law. Please discuss at least three examples.
9	Competition Policy in the EU: new trends	Discuss the (recent) developments in the EU Competition Policy, among them the "decentralization of the decision making" and the "private enforcement", as well as the "extraterritorial reach" of various competition measures (i.e., international dimension of the EU Competition Policy).
10	Industrial Policy and its role for business	This topic has a general focus and does not require an extensive discussion of the EU. It should be based on the general literature about the different forms of Industrial Policies. Examples - also international, e.g., from USA and China - are expected, but should be kept relatively short, with references to the sources for further information.
11	History and the latest developments in the EU Industrial Strategy	Specifically focus on two last waves of updates to the Industrial Policy reflecting the challenges of Covid and recent political and economic developments.
12	Environmental Policy in the EU	Provide a historical overview of major actions in the field of environmental sustainability. Focus on the environmental actions as part of the "double transition" strategy.

No.	TOPIC	COMMENTS
13	SMEs in the EU	Role of European institutional environment in supporting SMEs. What exactly is being done and how successfully.
14	Strategic dependencies	Focus on the discussions of Strategic Dependencies and Capacities published as updates to the Industrial Policy (2 waves).
15	Digital strategy in the EU	Overview of the current state of digitalization in the EU and the measures adopted to increase the level of digitalization (without focus on the Digital Compass).
16	Digital Compass: measuring progress of digitalization	Discuss the four areas outlined by the Digital Compass and explain how to measure the success through the DESI. Provide the examples of country-wise comparisons.
17	Employer-employee relations in the EU	European Pillar of Social Rights, Labour Law, and Working Time Directive as the basis for the employer-employee relations. Overview of the major documents protecting workers in their relationships with the employer. Comparison within and outside of the EU are welcome.
18	Free movement of labour in Europe	Discussion of rights and obligations on side of employees and employers. Please focus on the differences between EU nationals and third country nationals. Is there a free movement of labour in the EU after all?
19	Current trends in the Environmental Policy in the EU	Overview of the current trends, description of the selected most recent (last 5 years) policies. How to measure the progress? Is the EU on the right track to achieve the goals it set for itself?
20	Recent topics in the labour-related discussion	For example, discuss the collective bargaining agreements for self-employed, protection of platform workers, and initiatives for setting up the universal minimum wages, as well as other initiatives.

No.	TOPIC	COMMENTS
21	Posted workers and Undeclared labour	Discussion of these issues including a short introduction to the activities of ELA.
22	Institutional Financial support of SME	Discussion of the issues including a short introduction to the activities of EIF.
23	European Champions	Discussion of the idea, that Europe should promote the companies like Airbus, which show the example of strength and resilience as a result of joint effort of the member states. Are there other "European champions"? What is done to create them?

TAKE-HOME ESSAY (Revision of What Has Been Learnt)

To complete this assignment, the students are expected to go through the materials discussed in this course, lecture by lecture and make a short summary of what they have learned for each lecture (not more than 1 page per lecture).

While doing so, the students are encouraged to think which points, ideas, information were the most important for your understanding of the topic.

Additionally, the lecturer may ask students to include the answers to the following questions:

- Had you been asked to explain the topic to someone else, not familiar with it, what would you say?
- Which (further) sources would you recommend this person to read? Please offer at least three sources after each lecture's summary.
- Please also include the short overviews of the guest lectures in your discussion. What organizations were represented? What is their role in the EU? What were the main takeaways of each presentation for you?

The students should be warned against copy-pasting the materials from the lecture slides or any other sources., but paraphrase and provide proper references, where needed. The overall recommended length of the text may range between 4-7 pages (12 point Times New Roman font, single spaced page).

TAKE-HOME ESSAY (Online)

This Essay can also be administered online, but in this case the following instructions are suggested:

This is a take-home exam, which in this case means that students have 48 hours to complete it. They must answer _____ exam questions. You can earn up to _____ points.

Please make sure that you rely on the relevant external sources and properly cite them (use Harvard referencing style). You are expected to write at least 700 words per question (excluding the references). Please do not exceed the maximum words limit per question set at 1300 words.

Save the file in the .pdf format and upload it into the Exam Folder before _____ at _____.

Attention: If you do not upload your Exam paper into the Exam Folder within the designated time frame, you fail the exam (grade "insufficient") and the whole course.

Please be aware that the authenticity of your answers will be checked via the Turnitin function integrated in Moodle.

By technical problems, please make a screenshot of the error message on your screen and send it to the following email address.

Course Feedback

Modus: Anonym

IT IS ALL ABOUT YOU... AND THE COURSE

The course content was interesting ¹

1 - strongly agree 2 3 4 5 - strongly disagree

What was the most interesting topic for you? ¹

How many HOURS did you spend working on the CASE Project assigned to your team? (0 - 100) ¹

How many HOURS did you spend on the final Essay? (0 - 100) ¹

THE ISSUE WITH PARTICIPATION...

I participated in the course... ¹

1 - always very actively 2 3 4 5 - never

Most of the students participated in the course... ¹

1 - always very actively 2 3 4 5 - never

Why do you think the students didn't participate actively? What can be done to improve it?

What can be done to motivate you and other students to participate even more actively?

TEAM WORK

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement: "All members of the team actively participated in the team work" ¹

Yes No

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement: "All members of the team equally contributed to the team work" ¹

Yes No

How satisfied are you in general with the quality of your team work? ¹

1 - very satisfied 2 3 4 5 - very dissatisfied

Consider, what can be done to improve the quality of the teamwork, both by the students and by the lecturer. PLEASE SHARE!

This course fully met my expectations ¹

1 - strongly agree 2 3 4 5 - strongly disagree

I would recommend this course (or this instructor) to another student ¹

1 - strongly agree 2 3 4 5 - strongly disagree

Please share your overall opinion of the course in the space below. I will publish some of your testimonials on our project website. You can also provide your name, if you want.

¹ notwendig